

OPERATIONAL ENDURANCE OF VENEERS**Irgashev Shoxrux Xasanovich****Samarkand State Medical University**

Annotation: In recent decades, veneers have become popular as a method of minimally invasive cosmetic surgery treatment. Veneers can be made from materials with a variety of chemical properties, including materials based on a vitreous matrix, polycrystalline compositions, and ceramics based on a polymer matrix. The production of veneers with a high level of aesthetics is not considered a budgetary procedure, and people's demands on the conditions of use of veneers increase. The available literature contains data on the preservation of the ceramic composition for 3-20 years of satisfactory quality. At the same time, the cited sources provide quantitative data that characterize the violation of the aesthetic appearance of the tooth and veneers complex. To enhance the beauty of the smile, 38 patients for 6 years received veneers made of glass-ceramic material "IPS Empress Aesthetic" (n = 76) and hybrid material "Estenia" (n = 68) 144. When surgery was performed, 6.5% and 11% were diagnosed with complications, respectively. The article presents an approach that connects the violation of the aesthetic appearance of dental veneers with physiological and pathological changes in the chewing apparatus.

Keywords: veneers, complications, chewing apparatus, physiological and pathological changes

Introduction: Recently, there has been a tendency to increase the number of people who visit a dentist to improve the beauty and smile of their teeth [Liu et al., 2019]. The fact that the demand for veneers prosthetics is increasing is confirmed by the growing number of publications that reveal the features of this field of dentistry. The PubMed search engine, if you enter the keyword "dental veneers" in

1984 and 1986, will provide readers with 1 article, respectively, and in 2021 and 2022, 63 and 55 articles, respectively [PubMed]. The achievement of the "ideal" aesthetic (the aesthetic that the patient most desires in each particular case) is ensured by the ability to virtually plan its features before the actual dental procedure is initiated [Lo Giudice et al., 2020]. At the same time, one of the factors that determines the high demand for prosthetics with veneers is the ability to minimize the preparation of hard tooth tissues. The latest materials, clinical and laboratory algorithms make it possible to comply with minimally invasive techniques while maintaining the high aesthetic and strength characteristics of the veneer [Imburgia et al., 2019; Araujo, Perdigao, 2021]. The search for "ideal" aesthetics is particularly typical for young people who aspire to a high social status in society and, as a rule, maintain a high level of oral hygiene [Faus-Matoses et al., 2017]. In some cases, due to the lack of clinical indications for aesthetic prosthetics, young people tend to fix a whiter veneer in the oral cavity, which is significantly different in color from natural teeth. The adaptation of the mounting of veneers is perceived as a subjective and objective aesthetic problem. That is, abnormalities in the development of hard tooth tissues, discoloration of teeth of any nature, including due to enamel chips and cracks, the presence of a large number of fillings (caries), etc. From this it follows that, depending on the goal to be achieved, prosthetics with veneers should be considered in 2 ways: as a medical procedure, and the other - as an intervention aimed at increasing the likelihood of attractiveness and socialization. Relative contraindications to the placement of veneers include hypertrophied gingiva that cover the stump of the tooth, occlusal abnormalities with pathological wear of the tooth, prosthetic structures containing metal on antagonistic teeth, and defects in the dentition arches of class I and II, according to Kennedy. Absolute contraindications: increased sensitivity of the patient to components present in the fixation system [Alesina et al., 2014]. Compared to other orthopedic structures, that is, removable plates, bridges and single crowns known

to medical historians for hundreds and thousands of years, the manufacture of veneers is a fairly new dental tool. According to available data, the first veneers were made in 1928 by the California dentist Charles Pincus at the request of the Hollywood actor. Faced with high demand for methods of cosmetic prosthetics, C. Pincus continued laboratory and clinical research. In 1937, he introduced a cap made of acrylic and a special glue for fixing the cap to the front teeth. The acrylic cap could not withstand mechanical stress, and the adhesive melted under the influence of the intense environment in the oral cavity and sudden temperature changes. The combination of the observed complications led to the use of veneers as temporary cosmetic prosthetics, which are generally similar to nail polish. The developed cap bonding system was widely popular among artists and Hollywood employees, and the idiom "Hollywood Smile" was born. Наиболее популярная классификация содержит три обширные группы материалов для изготовления виниров: 1. керамика на основе стекловидной матрицы (стеклокерамика); 2) поликристаллическая керамика; 3) гибридная керамика на основе полимерной матрицы [American Dental Association]. The materials on the market are characterized by a variety of properties, depending on the technological process, which is of particular interest to practicing dentists.

Purpose: A comparative evaluation of the service life of veneers using IPS Empress Esthetic, a glass-ceramic material, and Estenia, a hybrid material. Materials and methods The study involved 18 patients who completed aesthetic prosthetics at the Interregional Dental Innovation Center (BelSU) and 20 who improved dental aesthetics at the Sadvaya Dental VladMiVa (VladMiVa), including 38 patients who participated in the study. The group formed in BelSU included 19 men and 18 women with a minimum age of 38, a maximum age of 28.89 ± 1.34 years with an average age of 8 and 10. The patient sample applied for VladMiVa consisted of 9 men and 11 women, with an average age of 29.90 ± 1.53 years, a minimum age of 17 years, and a maximum age of 43 years. The difference

in age characteristics in the study group is not statistically significant ($t = 0.50$, $p = 0.622577$). The criteria for inclusion in the sample population are: the hygiene index is not more than 13.3%, the dentition arch is complete, and if there are no teeth - The presence of a full-fledged bridge in the oral cavity, the absence of clinical symptoms of periodontitis, pathological wear of the teeth, and chronic general somatic pathology. The strict framework of age and clinical standards allows us to make the first hypothesis that the tooth and the veneers that cover it undergo a similar nominal (occlusal, chemical, biological) load. BelSU doctors installed 66 veneers, which equates to $1 \pm 3.67 \pm 0.38$ per person. VladMiV experts produced 78 veneers, that is, 3.90 ± 0.35 veneers per applicant. The difference in the number of veneers produced is not statistically significant ($t = 0.45$, $p = 0.656859$). Of the total number of veneers created from IPS Empress Esthetic material, 36 (2.0 ± 0.35) prostheses were created in BelSU and 40 (2.0 ± 0.52) in VladMiV. The difference in the number of glass-ceramic veneers produced is not statistically significant ($t = 0.00$, $p = 1.000000$). BelSU recorded 30 hybrid ceramic veneers, while VladMiV recorded 38, with averages of 1.67 ± 0.51 and 1.90 ± 0.50 , respectively. The difference in the number of veneers recorded in medical institutions is not statistically significant ($t = 0.32$, $p = 0.749343$). The fact that the difference in the number of veneers made of glass-ceramic and hybrid materials is unimportant is the basis for reliability, on which the number of complications depends, depending on the properties of the covering material and independently of the manual skills of the orthopedic team. The preparation of the teeth was carried out by polishing the enamel from the vestibular surface, while preparing the palate surface of the cutting edge. It is ambiguous whether such preparations are appropriate. It is recommended to prepare the cut edges for better aesthetics, load dispersion and proper fit. However, if the cutting edge is left intact, the cutting edge is excluded from the occlusal load, and the correct suitability of the veneers is determined by the other anatomical parts of the stump. Second, there is information in the literature

that the "survival rate" of veneers with cutting edge coating was 88% and 91% without cutting edge coating. That is, the longer the service life of a veneer with an intact cutting edge, the less reliable it is [Arif et al., 2019]. Fixing was made using light-cured polymer cement. After fixing the veneers, all the patients confirmed the improvement in the beauty of the smile. Before signing the documents confirming the receipt of the denture, the patient was strongly aware of the need to maintain good oral hygiene to minimize the occurrence of inflammation of the periodontal tissue. The need to avoid intensive or long-term ingestion of chewing gum was also explained. Recommendations for chewing gum are indicated to minimize the possibility of increased bite load, but do not exclude the possibility of deformation in the volume of cement and veneer. After that, patients were given the opportunity to undergo an annual follow-up examination and record the complaints that arose. According to the frequency of mention, the criteria for the failure of restorations included chipping, cracking, discoloration, shedding of veneers, the development of caries, increased reaction to temperature stimuli with the need for endodontic therapy, pathological reactions. Gum or periodontal tissue [Nejatidanesh et al., 2018]. Statistical differences in quantitative characteristics (group characteristics, number of veneers produced) were assessed by parametric analysis, that is, calculating the student's t-test for unrelated populations.

Results of the study: 1 year after strengthening the veneers, no one patient commented or complained about the installed structure. 2 years after the end of prosthetics, patient A received a complaint about the presence of subtle cracks on the surface of 2 sheets (2.9%) of veneers made of Estonian material. After 3 years, there were no complaints about the quality of aesthetic prosthetics. After 4 years, Patient B came to the hospital because the corners of 2 (2.6%) glass ionomer veneers that had been fixed to the left front tooth were missing. As a result of the examination, it was found that the patient had 5 implants implanted and the integrity of the mandibular dentition arch, characterized by a Kennedy Class I defect, was

restored. In this case, the chipping of the array should not be directly related to the performance characteristics of the material. This is because, in the presence of bilateral end defects, a decrease in the height of 3/1 under the face is observed with the corresponding redistribution. The effect of the bite load on the teeth, in which antagonists are present. During a clinical examination of the front tooth group, patient V was diagnosed with no significant deterioration in aesthetics and with a slight apical movement of the gums in the area of the middle incisors (2.9%) with hybrid ceramic veneers. In addition, under good hygiene conditions, the movement of the gums in the apical direction (1.0~3.0 mm) in the area of the middle incisor of the lower jaw was measured. At the same time, the patient noticed the appearance of increased sensitivity in the area of the teeth in the middle of the lower jaw, but did not receive complaints about the increased reaction of the upper teeth to temperature stimuli. She had a history of childbirth 7 months ago. After 5 years, when Patient V was examined, photographs taken immediately after the veneers were fixed and obtained during follow-up examinations, a low density arrangement of veneers was established without the formation of diastema. The patient did not notice the changes that occurred before the examination, but after the examination considered it unimportant. The patient does not complain of previously distressed pain, and the apical movement of the edge of the gums is not detected any more, this indicates the stabilization of the bite, the change should be considered postpartum. Patient G noticed a change in color in the cervical area of the hybrid ceramic veneers in the right incisors (2.9%). If you raise the upper lip and illuminate it with polarized light, then the color change will be reliably recorded. Detailing the situation, we found that the cause of the discoloration was due to the dissolution of the cement holding the veneer. The color change was considered insignificant, and the patient refused to remove the veneers. After 6 years, patient D underwent re-fixation of 3 collapsed (3.9%) glass ionomer veneers. Patient E also came to the hospital with complaints about the shedding of 2 sheets (2.9%) of hybrid ceramic

veneers. After processing the contact surface, glue the veneer with cement. During laboratory tests, the apical movement of the limbic gums in the area of the teeth with fixed veneers was revealed, but the patient did not show discoloration or other symptoms. On the condition of aesthetic prosthetics. An annual assessment of the condition of veneers made of glass-ceramic material "IPS Empress Esthetic", conducted over 6 years, revealed that the incidence of complications is 6.5%, and for veneers made of hybrid material "Estenia" - 11.3. %. The mean distribution of complications in the veneers set of "IPS Empress Esthetic" was 0.07 ± 0.03 , and in the case of "Estenia" was 0.12 ± 0.04 (this difference is not statistically significant). – 1.00, $p = 0.319024$). Consideration of the Results A study of the relevant literature led to an understanding of the ambiguity of the concept of "complications" related to clinically defined situations diagnosed in patients whose smile aesthetics were restored/modeled using veneers. To characterize a wide range of complications, the authors use such terms as "absolute", "relative", "unconditional" and "unsuccessful", characterizing different aspects of the diagnosis of the patient's dental condition. In many publications, the statistics that form a large number of clinical situations include "unconditional" complications such as postoperative hypersensitivity, recurrent caries requiring endodontic therapy (Beier et al., 2012; D'alcangelo et al., 2012. Guess et al., [2014]). Despite the fact that in these studies the duration of supervision of patients exceeds the period established by us, and the detected complications require invasive treatment, the percentage of veneers used without modification is very high. In other cases, only clinical situations requiring aesthetic work or a complete replacement of tooth extraction were considered "failed" treatment, and clinical situations previously cited as complications were not taken into account [Rinke et al., 2018]. It is possible that the material is cracked or chipped. Considering the mechanical factors that cause defects during prolonged use of veneers, the authors do not focus on the causes of defects. The physiological nature is different, but the reasons for the similarly increased load on veneers

include tooth wear, which forms reflex trauma nodules, and heterotrophic changes in periodontal tissues [Kopytov et al., [2011].At the same time, optimizing the occlusal relationship can minimize the load on the veneer material array and prevent mechanical defects.In our opinion, we believe that in the process of discussing the time of use of veneers, it is necessary to highlight the period during which certain clinical situations that require special attention or intervention are likely to occur.In addition, it is recommended to record not the symptoms of cosmetic disorders, but the causative factors that caused the complication.Therefore, according to the data obtained, within 3 years of using veneers, mechanical bite violations of the veneers array are most likely to occur.Mechanical stress damage was detected in 2.9% of hybrid ceramic veneers.Further complications are associated with changes in the function of the patient's chewing organs.This period may be limited to 4 to 6 years.Control tests revealed consistency violations of 2.6% glass ionomer and 2.9% hybrid ceramic veneers.This occurred during pregnancy and against the background of the restoration of the continuity of the dentition arch.In the late period, when the likelihood of breakage of the veneer due to the listed reasons does not decrease, complications, determined by the performance characteristics of the fixing material, become the most important.Because the integrity of the fixing cement was compromised, the 5.8% hybrid ceramic and 3.9% glass ionomer veneers needed to be re-fixed.

Conclusion: The statistics obtained do not characterize the performance characteristics of the material under consideration, but are determined primarily by physiological and pathological changes in the chewing apparatus.At the same time, the properties of the fixing material play an important role in the occurrence of complications, which are observed after 6 years of use of veneer.

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